

FREE AND TITRATABLE ACIDS PER PARTICLE OF SUBFRACTIONS OF HYDROGEN CLAY.*

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Subfractions having particle sizes ranging between specified limits have been separated from the entire clay fraction of a black cotton soil by controlled centrifugalisation following Ayre's technique as described by Whitt and Bayer (*J. Amer. Soc. Agron.*, 1937, 29, 917). Free and titratable acids of 0.25% suspensions of hydrogen clays prepared from them have been calculated respectively from the E.M.F. of the hydrogen electrode and the inflexion point of potentiometric titration curve with NaOH. If T is the free or titratable acid (in normality) per g. the corresponding quantity *per particle* is $4\pi^3 DT/3$, where $2r$ is the equivalent spherical diameter and D , the density. Also, the *number* of free or titratable H^+ ions per particle is the product of the free or titratable acid per particle and Avogadro's number. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Reference number of hydrogen clay.	Equivalent spherical diameter in microns.	Free acid (normality) per particle $\times 10^{23}$.	Titratable acid (in normality) per particle $\times 10^{23}$.	Number of free H^+ ions per particle.	Number of titratable H^+ ions per particle.
Pade-gaon-B -1	1.1	8.1×10^6	8.4×10^6	4.9×10^6	5.0×10^6
" -2	0.15	5.4×10^3	2.7×10^3	3.2×10^4	1.6×10^4
" -3	0.07	8.7×10^2	2.9×10^2	3.7×10^3	1.7×10^3
" -4	0.03	8.6×10	2.3×10	5.2×10^2	1.4×10^4
" -5	0.018	9.4	5.1	5.7×10	3.0×10^3

The number of free H^+ ions associated with the largest particles is of the order of 10^6 and that of titratable H^+ ions of the order of 10^6 . Both decrease rapidly with diminishing particle size. However, each particle of the finest subfraction has as many as 3×10^3 titratable H^+ ions. The titration curve of this as well as the other subfractions, however, reveals

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only a monobasic acid character. Other peculiarities of the titration curves have been discussed elsewhere (Mitra, *Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 1936, 6, 555; 1940, 10, 317; Mitra, *Bull. Indian Soc. Soil. Sci.*, 1942, No. 4, 41; Mukherjee, Mitra and Mukherjee, *Trans. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1937, 1, 227).

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